

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

Use Case: Offering Data to Service Providers with DataSpaces

To be able to measure the value offered by the DATAMITE framework it is ideal to be **tested over an actual use case that consists of data sharing to DataSpaces** and will be validated by publishing data in Energy DataSpaces like, potentially, those provided by DATA CELLAR.

Currently, [HEDNO](#) ensures the availability and statistical analysis of metering data while safeguarding consumers' personal information. However, sharing data with service providers remains a manual and complex process.

[Discover our Use Case!](#)

Campaign: Meet the people Behind DATAMITE

DATAMITE is an ambitious project with a consortium of 26 organisations from 11 countries, but beyond the numbers are the people. **With the series "Meet the people behind DATAMITE" we want to introduce the people who work every day to achieve our ambitious goal:** to deliver a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve data monetising, interoperability, trading and exchange in the form of software modules, training and business materials for European companies, empowering them to become new relevant players in the data economy.

[Read his full interview](#)

Samarkhel-Khan Yahya (DIN)

we present **Samarkhel-Khan Yahya** from [DIN](#) – the German Institute for Standardization. He studied Computer Science and Business Engineering in the field of project management, and since 2016, he works at DIN within the team responsible for the committee “Information Technology and selected IT Applications (NIA)”.

Ricardo Almeida Henriques (E-REDES)

We present **Ricardo Almeida Henriques** from [E-REDES](#) –the Portuguese main electricity distribution system operator. His role within DATAMITE is “to coordinate and contribute to the [E-REDES_pilot](#), called ‘leverage electricity distribution open data’”, he explains.

[Read his full interview](#)

Marko Turpeinen (1001 Lakes)

we present **Marko Turpeinen**, CEO at [1001 Lakes](#). In DATAMITE their role is “to be experts both in the technology side, especially regarding data quality and data usage control, and then also in the business legal and ethical questions that have to do with data monetization”, he explains.

[Read his full interview](#)

External & internal events

Launch Event: Showcasing the future of innovation in AI, Data, and Robotics, by Adra

On 9 February 2024 the “Launch Event: showcasing the future of innovation in AI, Data, and Robotics” took place, organised by [Adra-e](#). Santiago Cáceres, from [ITI](#) and coordinator of **DATAMITE**, was in charge of representing the project with a video-pitch that synthesised and illustrated in a simple way our main objectives.

DATAMITE at the Data Spaces Symposium 2024

From 12 to 14 March, the [Data Spaces Symposium](#) took place in Darmstadt (Germany). It is a pivotal gathering for those at the forefront of data space innovation and strategy. It included sessions from [Data Week 2024](#). **DATAMITE** was proud to be part of its programme, taking part in the session called ‘Navigating the Future of Data Monetisation: Insights from Horizon Europe projects’.

DATAMITE internal workshop - Exploitation Webinar

In order to foster a continuous exchange of knowledge among the partners, Antonis Sapountzis, leader of Work Package 6 (Outreach, Exploitation, and Collaboration), hosted an **internal webinar on exploitation**. Exploitation is the key to achieving wider impacts of DATAMITE in the longer term on the scientific community, the economy and society.

[Read more](#)[Read more](#)[Read more](#)

Women in Science Day: we are proud to be women scientists

Every 11th of February we celebrate the [International Day of women and Girls in Science](#). This milestone is a celebration but, moreover, it is a reminder of the need to achieve equality in **STEM** in order to not miss any possible talent. The DATAMITE consortium is acutely aware of the reality of inequality in the STEM sector and **fully supports measures to promote and establish real equality**, both within the project consortium and across the scientific community. That is why the women in the project shout out loud "**we are proud to be women scientists**".

[Watch their video](#)

eSAAM 2024 on Data Spaces

4th Eclipse Security, AI, Architecture and Modelling
on Data Spaces

October 22, Mainz, Germany

Co-organized by:

Call for papers: eSAAM 2024 on Data Spaces

The 4th Eclipse Security, Artificial Intelligence, Architecture, and Modelling (eSAAM) Conference on DATA SPACES will take place **22 October in Mainz, Germany**. This event is organised by Instituto Tecnológico de Informática ([ITI](#)), the coordinator of DATAMITE, along with the Centre for Research & Technology Hellas ([CERTH](#)), the [Eclipse Foundation](#), and the [University of Macedonia](#). The conference is an excellent platform for researchers to showcase their work to stakeholders from industry, standards bodies and open source initiatives, driving the evolution of data spaces. To this end, **a call for papers has been launched with a submission deadline of 12 May**.

[Submit your paper!](#)

EGI2024: Call for Abstracts!

[EGI2024](#) will be held from 30 September to 4 October in Lecce, Italy. The annual [EGI](#) conference brings together diverse **stakeholders from the broad scientific and data-intensive computing** domain.

The **call for Abstracts is now open**, with a **deadline of 25 April 2024!**

[More information](#)

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